

**UZBEKISTAN TOWARDS NEW DEVELOPMENT: A SEVEN-YEAR
STRATEGIC PLAN**

Mukhtorov Farruh Muhammadovich

**director of Fergana branch of Tashkent University of Information
Technologies, associate professor.**

Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna

**associate professor of the Department of Uzbek language
and humanitarian sciences, Fergana branch of Tashkent University of
Information Technologies.**

Abstract: The article says about the main purpose and tasks, demands and proposals of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev's Decree No. 158. September 11, 2023. The decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030" occupies an important place in the political, economic and social life of our country.

Keywords: Strategy, economy, state, task, plan

The decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030" occupies an important place in the political, economic and social life of our country, the role and importance of the important document will be briefly discussed in this study.

The essence of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy is intended for the next seven years, this programmatic document serving the country's development covers 5 priority directions containing 100 goals. All important tasks of socio-political and socio-economic development are defined in them.

The essence, goals, tasks, and priorities of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy are the main guarantee of establishing a legal, social, and secular democratic state in our country, ensuring human interests, rights and freedoms, and improving the

development of our economy and the well-being of our lives.

September 11, 2023 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. The main goal of Mirziyoyev's Decree No. 158 is to realize the desire of our people to build a free and prosperous, powerful New Uzbekistan, to create all opportunities for every citizen to develop their potential, to create a healthy, educated and education of a morally mature generation, formation of a strong economy that has become an important link of global production, guaranteeing justice, rule of law, security and stability. It is taken into account that the following main ideas are reflected in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy:

- to take a place among countries with higher than average income through stable economic growth;
- organization of educational, medical and social protection system fully meeting the requirements of the population and international standards;
- creation of favorable environmental conditions for the population;
- establishment of a fair and modern state in the service of the people;
- guaranteed provision of sovereignty and security of the country.

It was emphasized that the implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and the achievement of its target indicators is the most important task in the activities of all state bodies and organizations.

Within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, it is necessary for everyone to know that achieving all the goals, which have not lost their importance, are defined in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan and continue to be implemented. It stipulates the organization of full, timely and high-quality implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, as well as the preparation and coordination of the implementation of relevant annual programs for its implementation.

The head of the country is responsible for quality implementation of reform measures within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy based on the opinions and initiatives expressed by the population, monitoring the achievement

of the specified indicators, and providing information about the results to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan every six months. It is not for nothing that the minister was entrusted with it. In addition, the results of the implementation of the New Uzbekistan development strategy on the ground are critically studied.

Wide discussion of the results of the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan among the population throughout the republic, systematic analysis of citizens' proposals on this issue will serve to quickly implement the tasks set in this decree. tasks are set:

- according to the results of the conducted studies, to determine the systemic factors that prevent the realization of the goals and tasks set in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan and to prevent them within the framework of the implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy to ensure that specific measures are taken;

- To hear and critically discuss the information of the heads of territorial divisions of the ministries and agencies on the regional implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy to the Dzhokorg Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Councils of People's Deputies of the regions and the city of Tashkent;

The demands and proposals given by President Sh. Mirziyoyev regarding the implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and practical measures for its implementation, on the achievement of relevant target indicators and the timely development of regulatory legal documents within them intends to carry out the control in an appropriate manner.

It is worth noting that in the decree, together with the Ministry of Digital Technologies, within two weeks, the level of implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the evaluation of the qualitative implementation of the reforms specified in it by the population in terms of each goal and its indicators, they were given the task of launching an online portal that would create an opportunity to leave their opinions and take initiatives. The issue of summarizing the opinions of

the population regarding the various reforms being carried out in the country and forming a commission that will resolve them positively was also put forward.

Preparation of informational and analytical comments on the results of the implementation of the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" and the measures for its implementation in the relevant years, their publication in foreign languages and provision of wide distribution is determined. the article will undoubtedly be a performance of tasks in this direction.

In addition, mass media have been assigned major tasks, and the Information and Mass Communications Agency, the National Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan, and the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan have been appointed to be responsible for their implementation. The main tasks they have to perform are:

- wide interpretation of the goals and tasks set in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy in mass media, including the Internet global information network and social networks, and its content and essence to be communicated to the public;

- It was determined to provide impartial and complete information to the population regarding the implementation of the measures implemented within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and the status of achieving the set target indicators.

It is decided to discuss the implementation of this Decree every six months, and it is expected that 6-7 discussions will be held until 2030.

In conclusion, it can be said that The decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" serves to implement reforms in the political, economic, social and cultural aspects of our country based on the interests of the people. It is clear that it gives the citizen a sense of pride.

List of used literature

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони, 11.09.2023 йилдаги ПФ-158-сон. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6600413>

2. Вебер М. Политика как призвание и профессия// Диалог.1993. № 5, 6. 29. Винер Н. Кибернетика и общество. —Москва: 1958.
3. Винер Н. Кибернетика или управление и связь в животном и машине. —Москва: 1983. 31. Гегель Г.В.Ф. Философия права. —Москва: Мысль, 1990.
4. Гекторн Чарльз Уильям. Тайны общества всех веков и всех стран. —Ташкент: Шарк, 1994. 33. Глухова А.В. Политические конфликты: основания, типология, динамика (теоретико-методологический анализ) — Москва: Эдиториал УРСС, 2000. 34. Гоббс Т. И

